

Mohacūrottara, chapter 3, verses 29-36a, edition

[I will treat only that portion of the chapter that deals with the brahmaśilā, verses 29-36a, beginning the edition at the end of the section on the piṇḍikā, and ending before the section on the pīṭha.]

F f20v, line 4; G (the folios appear scrambled. I will refer to the digital image number) 008.tif, lower, line 1; H f10v, line 2.

- 3.29 iti piṇḍī samākhyātā vakṣye brahmaśilāṃ tava
brahmabhāgasamā bhadrā kāryā brahmaśilā śubhā
- 3.30 digāṅgulair yathā vyāsād adhikā jyeṣṭhajyeṣṭhake F21r
ekaikāṅgulam anyeṣāṃ hrāsayet kramato hare
- 3.31 tanmānā mekhalā kāryā khātaṃ mekhalayā samam
gambhīraṃ tat samuddiṣṭam vyāsaṃ vacmi tavādhunā
- 3.32 brahmavyāseṇa vistīrṇam adhikaṃ ṣaḍyavaṃ bahiḥ
yavārdhārdhaṃ tu cānyeṣāṃ hrāsayet kramaśaḥ punaḥ
- 3.33 adhikaṃ vistareṇaiva kanyase dviyavaṃ bhavet
sūtreṇa sammitaṃ kṛtvā vartayet sutalaṃ samam
- 3.34 khātamadhye tu yatnena ratnādhārāṇi cotkiret
digvidikṣu tato madhye vṛttavat parikalpayet
- 3.35 yathā brahmaśilā kāryā brahmabhāgādhikā hare F21v
tathā kūrmaśilāṃ kuryāt kiṃtu brahmaśilādhikāṃ
- 3.36 iti brahmaśilā caiva

Ω = F(→H)G

29b tava] FH; ta{va} G 29c bhadrā] FH; khyātā G 32d kramaśaḥ] em.; kramasaḥ
FG; kramataḥ H 33b kanyase dvi] FH; karmmasiddhir G
33c sammitaṃ] FH; sumitaṃ G 33d sutalaṃ] FH; sutala G
34c madhye] GH; {madhye} F 35d śilādhikāṃ] H; śilādhikāṃ F; śilādhikā G